

A Study on Green Marketing in India

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Abstract

Green marketing is the marketing of products presumed to be environmentally safe. Green marketing incorporates a broad range of activities, including Product modification, Changes to the production process, Packaging changes and Modifying advertising. Ultimately it looks at how marketing activities utilize these limited resources while satisfying consumers want, both of individuals and organization as well as achieving the sales objectives of the organization. Even till date, it has not been inculcated as a subject in identifying the key ideas about the awareness of green products that may be most relevant to the eco-friendly environment. This paper attempts to examine the concept of green marketing, various challenges and opportunities associated with it, and initiative taken by Government in India to realize the concept of making in India.

Keywords: Consumers, Green Marketing, Purchase Intentions and Green Products.

Introduction

First of all, environment and environmental problems, one of the reasons why the green marketing emerged. According to the American Marketing Association, green marketing is the marketing of products that are presumed to be environmentally safe. Thus green marketing incorporates a broad range of activities, including product modification, changes to the production process, packaging changes, as well as modifying advertising. Green marketing refers to holistic marketing concept wherein the product, marketing consumption on disposal of products and services happen in a manner that is less detrimental to the environment with growing awareness about the implications of global warming, non-biodegradable solid waste, harmful impact of pollutants, etc., both marketers and consumers are becoming increasingly sensitive to the need to switch into green products and services. Many people believe that green marketing refers solely to the promotion and advertising of products with environmental characteristics. Generally, terms like phosphate free, recyclable, refillable, ozone friendly and environment friendly are most of the things consumers often associated with green marketing.

Green marketing is a golden goose. As per Mr. J. Polonsky, green

marketing can be defined as, “All activities designed to generate and facilitate any exchange intended to satisfy human needs or wants such that satisfying of their needs and wants to occur with minimal detrimental input on the national environment.” Green marketing is also called environmental marketing/ecological marketing. As resources are limited and human wants are unlimited, it is important for the marketers to utilize the resources efficiently without waste as well as to achieve the organization’s objective. So green marketing is inevitable. There is growing interest among the consumers all over the world regarding the protection of the environment. Worldwide evidence indicates people are concerned about the environment and are changing their behavior. As a result of this, green marketing has emerged which speaks for the growing market for sustainable and socially responsible products and services. Now, this has become the new mantra for marketers to satisfy the needs of consumers and earn better profits.

Evolution of Green Marketing

Green marketing term was first discussed in a seminar on —Ecological Marketing- organized by American Marketing Association (AMA) in 1975 and took its place in the literature. The term green marketing came into prominence in the late 1980s and early 1990s. The first wave of green marketing occurred in the 1980s. The tangible milestone for the first wave of green marketing came in the form of published books, both of which were called Green Marketing. They were by Ken Peattie (1992) in the United Kingdom and by Jacquelyn Ottman (1993) in the United States of America. According to Peattie (2001), the evolution of green marketing has three phases.

The first phase was termed as “Ecological” green marketing, and during this period all marketing activities were concerned to help environmental problems and provide remedies for environmental problems.

The second phase was “Environmental” green marketing, and the focus shifted on clean technology that involved designing of innovative new products, which take care of pollution and waste issues.

The third phase was “Sustainable” green marketing. It came into prominence in the late 1990s and early 2000 concerned with developing good quality products which can meet consumers need by focusing on the quality, performance, pricing and convenience in an environment friendly way.

Objectives of the Study

The paper titled —Green marketing in India: An overview is aimed to cover the following objectives:

- To know the concept of green marketing.
- To identify the importance and need for green marketing.
- To study the challenges and prospects of green marketing.

Research Methodology

The research is exploratory; it focuses on Literature review, News Papers, Journals, websites and the other reliable sources.

Review of Literature

Donaldson (2005) in his study realized in Great Britain that in general, the ecological attitude of consumers changed positively. This study reported the strong faith of consumers in the known commercial brands and in the feeble behavior referring to the “green” claims, which was the main cause behind the consuming failure to interpret their concerns beyond the environment in their behavior.

Alsmadi (2007) while investigating the environmental behavior of Jordanian consumers reveals a high level of environmental conscience. Unfortunately, however, this positive tendency

and preference in the “green” products did not appear to have any effect on the final decision, obviously because these consumers had a stronger faith in the traditional products and small confidence in the green statements. The above obstacles were further strengthened by the lack of environmental conscience by a lot of enterprises and the existence of a large scale of prices for the same product, many of which included an impetuous estimate of environmental responsibility. The same phenomenon has been presented in other researches too (Ottman, 2004; Donaldson, 2005; Cleveland et al., 2005).

Brahma, M. & Dande, R. (2008) The Economic Times, Mumbai, had an article which stated that Green Ventures India is a subsidiary of New York-based asset management firm Green Ventures International. The latter recently announced a \$300 million India focused fund aimed at renewable energy products and supporting trading in carbon credits.

Golden Rules of Green Marketing

- Know your Customer: Make sure that the consumer is aware of and concerned about the issues that your product attempts to address.
- Educating your customers: It is not just a matter of letting people know, whatever you’re doing is to protect the environment, but also a matter of letting them know why it matters.
- Being Genuine & Transparent: means that a) You are doing what you claim to be doing in your green marketing campaign and b) The rest of your business policies are consistent with whatever you are doing that’s environment friendly.
- Reassure the Buyer: Consumers must be made to believe that the product performs the job, in this film should not forget product quality in the name of the environment.
- Consider Your Pricing: If you are charging a premium for your product and many environmentally preferable products cost more due to economies of scale and use of higher-quality ingredients make sure those consumers can afford the premium and feel it’s worth it.

Countries Ranked According to Their Responding Level on Green Marketing

Rank	Countries
1	India
2	UK
3	US
4	Thailand
5	Australia
6	Canada
7	China

Source: Namex International Journal of Management Research

The Four Ps of Green Marketing

Product

Entrepreneurs are wanting to exploit the emerging green market either by identifying customer’s environmental needs or by developing environmentally responsible products to have less impact than competitors. The increasingly development of :

- Products that can be recycled or reused. Efficient products, which save water, energy or gasoline, save money and reduce environmental impact.
- Products with environmentally responsible packaging. McDonald’s, for example, changed their packaging from polystyrene clamshells to paper.

- Products with green labels, as long as they offer substantiation.
- Organic products — many consumers are prepared to pay a premium for organic products, which offer the promise of quality. Organic butchers, for example, promote the added qualities such as taste and tenderness.
- A service that rents or loans products —such as toy libraries.
- Certified products, which meet or exceed environmentally responsible criteria.

Whatever the product or service, it is vital to ensure that products meet or exceed the quality expectations of customers and is thoroughly tested.

Price

Pricing is a critical element of the marketing mix. Most customers are prepared to pay a premium if there is a perception of additional product value. This value may be improved performance, function, design, visual appeal or taste. Environmental benefits are usually a bonus but will often be the deciding factor between products of equal value and quality. Environmentally responsible products, however, are often less expensive when product life cycle costs are taken into consideration, for example, fuel-efficient vehicles, water-efficient printing and non-hazardous products.

Place

The choice of where and when to make a product available has a significant impact on the customers being attracted. Very few customers go out of their way to buy green products merely for the sake of it. Marketers looking to successfully introduce new green products should, in most cases, position them broadly in the market place, so they are not just appealing to a small green niche market. The location must also be consistent with the image which a company wants to project. The location must differentiate a company from its competitors. This can be achieved by in-store promotions and visually appealing displays or using recycled materials to emphasize the environmental and other benefits.

Promotion

Promoting products and services to target markets includes paid advertising, public relations, sales promotions, direct marketing and on-site promotions. Smart green marketers will be able to reinforce environmental credibility by using sustainable marketing and communications tools and practices. For example, many companies in the financial industry are providing electronic statements by email, e-marketing is rapidly replacing more traditional marketing methods, and printed materials can be produced using recycled materials and efficient processes, such as waterless printing. Retailers, for example, are recognizing the value of alliances with other companies, environmental groups and research organizations when promoting their environmental commitment. To reduce the use of plastic bags and promote their green commitment, some retailers sell shopping bags, under the banner of the Go Green Environment Fund. The key to successful green marketing is credibility. Never overstate environmental claims or establish unrealistic expectations, and communicate simply and through sources that people trust. Promote your green credentials and achievements. Publicize stories of the company's an environmental awards programs to profile environmental credentials to customers and stakeholders.

Green Washing

“Consumers do not really understand a lot about these issues on Green marketing, and there's a lot of confusion out there in the minds of the customer about what actually green marketing is

all about,” says Jacquelyn Ottman (Author of “Green Marketing: Opportunity for Innovation.”) Marketers sometimes take advantage of this confusion, and purposely make false or exaggerated “green” claims. Critics refer to this practice as “green washing” which means trying to sell the customers those products which are not environment friendly but the company claims them to be environment friendly.

Green Products in India

Wipro Info tech (Green It) was India’s first company to launch environment friendly computer peripherals. Samsung was the first to launch eco-friendly mobile handsets (made of renewable materials) – W510 and F268- in India. Oil and Natural Gas Corporation Ltd. (ONGC), India’s largest oil company, has introduced energy-efficient Mokshada Green Crematorium, which saves 60% to 70% of wood and a fourth of the burning time per cremation. Reva, India’s very-own Bangalore based company, was the first in the world to commercially release an electric car. Honda India introduced its Civic Hybrid car. ITC has introduced Paper Kraft, a premium range of eco-friendly business paper. Indusland Bank installed the country’s first solar-powered ATM and thus brought about an eco-savvy change in the Indian banking sector. Suzlon Energy manufactures and markets wind turbines, which provide an alternative source of energy based on wind power. This green initiative taken by the company is extremely important in reducing the carbon footprint.

Green Marketing- Challenges

Although a large number of firms are practicing green marketing, it is not an easy job as there are some problems which need to be addressed while implementing Green marketing. The major challenges which Green marketing have to be faced are:

New Concept: Indian literate and the urban consumer is getting more aware of the merits of Green products. But it is still a new concept for the masses. The consumer needs to be educated and made aware of the environmental threats. The new green movements need to reach the masses and that will take a lot of time and effort.

Cost Factor: Green marketing involves marketing of green products/services, green technology, green power/energy for which a lot of money has to be spent on R&D programmes for their development and subsequent promotional programs which ultimately may lead to increased costs.

Convincing Customers: The customers may not believe in the firm’s strategy of Green marketing; the firm, therefore, should ensure that they undertake all possible measures to convince the customer about their green product, the best possible option is by implementing Eco-labeling schemes. Sometimes the customers may also not be willing to pay the extra price for the products.

Sustainability: Initially the profits are very low since renewable and recyclable products and green technologies are more expensive. Green marketing will be successful only in the long run. Hence the business needs to plan for the long-term rather than short-term strategy and prepare for the same, at the same time it should avoid falling into the lure of unethical practices to make profits in the short term.

Non Cooperation: The firms practicing Green marketing have to strive hard in convincing the stakeholders and many times it may fail to convince them about the long-term benefits of Green marketing as compared to short-term expenses.

Avoiding Green Myopia: Green marketing must satisfy two objectives: improved environmental quality and customer satisfaction. Misjudging either or overemphasizing the former at the expense of the latter can be termed green marketing myopia.

Suggestions

Green marketing is still in its infancy and a lot of research is to be done on green marketing to fully explore its potential. There is some suggestion that organizations should implement for

catering challenges of green marketing and successful exploitation of green marketing.

The consumer needs to be made more aware of the merits of Green products. The consumer needs to be educated and made aware of the environmental threats. It should be made sure that the consumer is aware of and concerned about the issues that your product attempts to address. Green Marketing campaign and green advertising is the good step toward it. Consumers must be motivated to switch brands or even pay a premium for the greener alternative.

Make sure that the consumer feels that they can make a difference. This is called empowerment and due to this main reason, consumers will buy greener products. Further steps should be taken to control false promise and claim by the marketer to maintain legitimacy and trust worthiness of green products. For the effective and efficient implementation of this concept of Green Marketing the factor that plays a major role is the Government. Unless the government creates specific and stringent laws and utilizes its authority to implement them, the concept cannot be conceptualized. If the Consumer, the Organization and the Government work in unison towards the common goal of minimizing the detrimental environmental impact of their activities, then they can surely save this environment and make this world a better place to live in. It is not enough for a company to green its products, consumers expect the products at they purchase pocket-friendly and also to help reduce the environmental impact in their own lives too. Green marketing is very low on the agenda of most businesses and therefore it's still an under-leveraged USP (Unique Selling Proposition). Therefore, effective green marketing targeted at the right audience will make a difference.

Conclusion

Green marketing is a tool for protecting the environment for future generation. It is not going to be an easy concept. The firm has to plan and then carry out research to find out how feasible it is going to be. Green marketing has to evolve since it is still in its infancy stage. Adoption of Green marketing may not be easy in the short run, but in the long run, it will have a positive impact on the firm. Green Marketing is still in the stage of childhood in the Indian companies. Lots of opportunities are available. Now, this is the right time to select Green Marketing globally. It will come with the drastic change in the world of business if all nations make strict rules because green marketing is essential to save the world from pollution. From the business point of view because a clever marketer is one who not only convinces the consumer but also involves the consumer in marketing his product. Green marketing should not be considered as just one more approach to marketing but has to be pursued with much greater vigor, as it has an environmental and social dimension to it. With the threat of global warming looming large, it is extremely important that green marketing becomes the norm rather than an exception or just a fad. Recycling of paper, metals, plastics, etc., in a safe and environmentally harmless manner should become much more systematized and universal. It has to become the general norm to use energy efficient lamps and other electrical goods.

Indian market Customers too are ready to pay the premium price for green products. One thing that is being reiterated is that the current consumption levels are too high and are unsustainable. An environmental committed organization may not only produce goods that have reduced their detrimental impact on the environment, but they may also be able to pressure their suppliers to behave in a more environmentally responsible fashion. Final consumers and industrial buyers also can pressure organizations to integrate the environment into their corporate culture and thus ensure all organizations minimize the detrimental environmental impact of their activities.

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